

Imploring the Atom : Nuclear plant lifespan extensions

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Many African countries are increasingly considering nuclear energy to diversify their energy mix. A world that is no longer going to be dependent on a large fossil fuel resource, will face dramatic unplanned changes that would be impossible to manage. Both developed and developing (China, Japan, India and South Korea) countries have invested heavily in nuclear energy. A number of political, financial and economy based challenges remain in South Africa that will need to be addressed before expansion of our nuclear programme can be undertaken.

One of the most difficult problems associated with nuclear power is the disposal of waste produced during mining, fuel production, and reactor operation. The fundamental safety objective is to protect people and the environment from harmful effects of ionizing radiation, especially with ageing infrastructure. The need to systematically identify and address all environmental and safety concerns, and developing an Integrated Implementation Plan is required. A new environmental assessment (EA) process and an Integrated Safety Review (ISR) must be performed.

The ISR assess the plant design, condition, and operation according to the Periodic Safety Review of Nuclear Power Plants – Safety Guide (IAEA PSR Guide) published by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). New knowledge from R&D and advances in technology are taken into account. This enables determination of reasonable and practical modifications that should be made to systems, structures, and components, and to management arrangements, to enhance the safety of the old facility to a level approaching that of a modern power plant. Non-compliance with modern standards and practices should be resolved. Concrete and water ingress, instrumentation upgrades and new control techniques will have to be assessed against the plant's existing operational framework.

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